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**CLINICAL AND DIAGNOSTIC SIGNIFICANCE OF ENDOTHELIAL
DYSFUNCTION IN TYPE 1 DIABETES MELLITUS IN CHILDREN**

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Abstract: *The purpose of this review is to examine materials devoted to complications of type 1 diabetes in children and to analyze markers of vascular wall damage involved in the development of angiopathies.*

Key words: *children and adolescents, diabetes mellitus, type 1 diabetes, endothelial dysfunction, endocrine diseases.*

INTRODUCTION

Type 1 diabetes mellitus (T1DM), being one of the most severe endocrine diseases of children and adolescents, remains a major medical and social problem, which is associated with a progressive increase in the number of patients, a high degree of disability of patients and premature death, including young people. Such an unfavorable course of T1DM is associated with the development of chronic vascular complications (micro- and macroangiopathies). Microangiopathy (MAP) is specific to diabetes, among which diabetic retinopathy, nephropathy and neuropathy pose the greatest threat to health.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

We conducted a search for literary sources in scientific article indexing databases and open repositories. The main part of the presented data was taken from the search databases PubMed, Google Scholar.

In this regard, the aim of this study was to investigate the content of endothelial factors – metabolites of nitric oxide (NO_x), endothelin-1 (ET-1) and basic fibroblast growth factor (bFGF) in children and adolescents with type 1 diabetes, taking into account the formation of DPNP in them.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Diabetes mellitus is caused by impaired insulin secretion (type 1) or peripheral insulin resistance (type 2), which subsequently leads to the development of hyperglycemia. Early symptoms include polydipsia, polyphagia, polyuria, and weight loss, and are associated with the development of hyperglycemia in the

patient. The diagnosis is established based on the results of fluctuations in plasma glucose levels.

In children with type 1 diabetes, the main factors contributing to the development of late complications are the duration of the disease, the period of puberty and the presence of chronic hyperglycemia due to decompensation of the disease. In addition, there are other risk factors for endothelial damage, such as hypercholesterolemia, hyperhomocysteinemia and elevated cytokine levels [1]. It is they, taken together, with a long-term effect on the vascular and nervous systems, that contribute to changes in various target organs, leading to the development of late complications of diabetes mellitus. Such complications include microangiopathy (diabetic retinopathy and diabetic nephropathy), macroangiopathy (ischemic heart disease, ischemic brain disease, atherosclerosis of the vessels of the lower extremities), neuropathy (peripheral and autonomic forms).

The adverse effect of glycemic instability and chronic hyperglycemia on the functional state of the vascular endothelium with the development of endothelial dysfunction (ED) has been noted [2]. Increased desquamative processes in the endothelium in children with type 1 diabetes are observed already at the manifestation of the disease; if it lasts more than a year, depletion of endothelium-dependent vasodilation occurs; if it lasts more than three years, signs of deendothelialization of the vascular wall appear, which causes hemodynamic impairment and is one of the pathogenetic mechanisms for the formation of diabetic microangiopathies of various localizations. It has been proven that patients suffering from diabetes mellitus have an increase in the concentration of vasoconstrictors, namely ET-1 (the longer the disease lasts, the higher the ET level), and a decrease in the synthesis of vasodilators, such as prostacyclin and nitric oxide. In addition, there is an increase in the activity of platelet/endothelial cell adhesion molecules, thrombogenic endothelial biomarkers - tissue factor, plasminogen activator inhibitor-1, as well as the expression of adhesion molecules of the immunoglobulin and selectin family [3].

It has also been established that it is hyperglycemia that contributes to a greater extent to the alteration of the glycocalyx of endothelial cells, resulting in a change in the barrier function of the vessel wall and an increase in its adhesive properties. In the presence of hyperglycemia in the body, the rate of NO diffusion to smooth muscle cells decreases, the availability of the NO precursor L-arginine is inhibited, the destruction of NO by free radicals increases, under the influence of which the inactivation of various vasodilators is accelerated. Currently, a theory has been put forward that under hyperglycemia conditions, the fundamental role in the development of diabetic micro- and macroangiopathies is attributed to oxidative

stress as a result of an imbalance between the production and utilization of reactive oxygen species. As a result of this imbalance, they accumulate, due to which reactive oxygen species begin to act damagingly, causing oxidative modification of proteins, lipids and nucleic acids, which can lead to disruption of various functions, and subsequently to cell death [5]. Activation of lipid peroxidation, formation of modified lipoproteins, an increase in their number in foam cells are markers of ED in diabetes mellitus. Under physiological conditions, endothelial NOS is a dimer that produces NO. Dimerization of NOS occurs under the influence of the cofactor tetrahydrobiopterin, and in diabetes mellitus there is a decrease in the amount of this factor, due to which NOS actively produces superoxide radicals, which, in turn, oxidize tetrahydrobiopterin, the vicious circle is closed, and the decrease in NO production becomes even more noticeable [7]. A decrease in the amount of NO subsequently causes a violation of vasomotor activity, thromboresistance, barrier and angiogenic functions of endothelial cells. During the glycosylation reaction, glucose combines with various residues of amino acid proteins into compounds that, in turn, are a precursor for the formation of advanced glycation products and active oxygen species. It has been established that the higher the blood glucose level, the more advanced glycation products are determined. And their level remains high even if the glucose level is normalized. In addition, glycosylated forms are formed with virtually all types of proteins: albumin, hemoglobin, lipoproteins, the lens of the eye, collagen, causing damage to their structure. For example, glycosylation of albumin contributes to changes in the transport of fatty acids, bilirubin and drugs, as well as the development of diabetic nephropathy due to accumulation in the basal membrane of the renal glomeruli. Glycosylation of hemoglobin enhances its connection with oxygen, causing hypoxia of various tissues. During glycosylation of lipoproteins, receptor recognition is impaired and their time in the bloodstream increases, which in turn contributes to increased atherosclerotic damage to the vascular wall [8].

Glycosylation of lens proteins contributes to the disruption of the light transmission reaction, resulting in the formation of diabetic cataract. Glycosylation of collagen causes a change in its physicochemical properties, causing a decrease in solubility and an increase in resistance to collagenase. All this contributes to the formation of endothelial dysfunction due to the disruption of the barrier function of the vascular wall, an increase in the expression of adhesive molecules, the formation of reactive oxygen species, an increase in the expression of inducible NOS by advanced glycation end products, as well as a decrease in the content and availability of NO. In addition, in addition to hyperglycemia, other factors such as dyslipidemia, intraglomerular hypertension and cytokines play a major role in the pathogenesis of ED, which contribute to the disruption of the integrity of the vascular endothelium

and provoke the release of various damage mediators: angiotensins, cytokines, C-reactive protein, endothelins, tumor necrosis factor, etc., as a result of which diabetic complications are formed [9]. Based on the results of the works of various authors, it can be concluded that the obtained data on the role of ET 1-21 in the development of diabetic micro- and macroangiopathies are ambiguous. The greatest number of researchers came to the conclusion that, nevertheless, in patients with complications, the ET level was noted to be higher than normal, in contrast to children who had not yet developed complications. Although in the work of the author V.N. Panfilova and co-authors, this pattern in the development of diabetic retinopathy and polyneuropathy was not revealed [10]. Correction of endothelial dysfunction in type 1 diabetes is considered a fairly promising direction aimed at finding effective methods for the prevention and treatment of various complications of this disease in children. In the development of diabetic microangiopathies, another, and most important, link is a decrease in the content of glycosaminoglycans (GAG) in the vascular system of the glomeruli and mesangial matrix. That is why doctors have recently increasingly resorted to the use of drugs belonging to the GAG group. One of such drugs of this group, actively used, including in children and adolescents, is sulodexide (Vessel Due F). Sulodexide is an anticoagulant, the active substance of which is an extract from the mucous membrane of the small intestine of animals, which is a natural mixture of a fast-moving heparin-like fraction (80%) and dermatan sulfate (20%). Sulodexide performs all sorts of functions: inhibits activated factor X, increases the production of prostacyclin, reduces the content of fibrinogen in plasma, increases the amount of plasminogen in the blood and reduces the amount of its inhibitor [11]. The drug is available in two dosage forms: in the form of capsules of 250 LE and a solution for intravenous and intramuscular administration of 600 LE/2 ml, and the treatment is prescribed in addition to the standard therapy of diabetes, which includes insulin therapy, diet therapy, symptomatic therapy. According to the research of Nikolaeva N.V. It was found that during the use of the drug sulodexide, the general condition of most patients improved, children and their parents complained less, some patients had a decrease in albuminuria, manifestations of angiopathy in the fundus, and an increase in the speed of impulse conduction along the peripheral nerves of the extremities. But after completing the full course of treatment, children with a history of the disease of up to 5 years showed a decrease in the rate of platelet aggregation and an increase in the time of their aggregation, an increase in the antiaggregatory, anticoagulant and fibrinolytic activity of the vascular wall and some indicators of the coagulation link of the hemostasis system: antithrombin III activity and fibrinolytic activity of the blood.

Moreover, no reliably detected changes in these indicators in children suffering from type 1 diabetes for more than 5 years [12].

In addition to the above study, there are results of a number of authors on the use of sulodexide in children with a complication in the form of diabetic nephropathy. A decrease in the level of microalbuminuria and proteinuria, as well as a decrease in the content of protein and glucose in the urine were noted in all the children studied. In 38% of children, the proteinuric stage passed into the stage of microalbuminuria, and in the same number of patients, microalbuminuria completely disappeared in the tests. An improvement in the values of endogenous creatinine clearance, a decrease in the atherogenic coefficient of blood serum and triglyceride levels were noted, i.e. an atherogenic effect of the drug was noted. The authors also note that the most effective use of the drug was noted in patients with newly diagnosed microalbuminuria [13]. The effect of sulodexide was also studied in patients with diabetes mellitus who have a history of such a complication as diabetic retinopathy. Such patients showed an improvement in the condition of the retinal vessels, and a greater effect was achieved with the combined use of this drug with laser coagulation [14]. In addition, N.A. Gavrilov and O.E. Tishchenko studied the effect of sulodexide on ED indices. The authors note that in all patients, the level of endothelial factors such as sVCAM, endothelin, nitric oxide, fibrinolytic activity of the vascular wall, glycoprotein was initially changed, and after a course of therapy, a normal level of these indices was already noticeable. However, there are no data on the use of sulodexide specifically in children with diabetic retinopathy [15].

CONCLUSION

Effective methods of prevention and treatment of diabetic angiopathies in children are an important task for any clinician, the solution of which requires a clear understanding of the links of pathogenesis in order to influence them already at the early stages of disorders. Currently, one of such drugs with a positive effect is sulodexide. The example of its use clearly shows that this type of treatment should be prescribed precisely in the first 5 years of diabetes, since later use of this drug does not cause such pronounced changes in ED indices, and therefore a decrease in the manifestations of diabetic complications. Despite the growing interest and a huge number of studies on this topic, many aspects remain not fully understood or are contradictory among different authors, which makes it necessary to further study the role of ED in children with type 1 diabetes, and also necessitates more frequent use of the drug sulodexide in the pediatric population.

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